

An Improved Check Valve for Vacuum Pumps.

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It is a matter of common experience with vacuum pumps that even slight diminution in the rate of evacuation leads to the undesirable phenomenon of 'back-suction' often resulting in the spoilage of the experiments in progress. Moreover, the methods generally adopted for maintaining vacua are highly wasteful requiring continuous use of energy or constant flow of water often over several hours. There is need, therefore, for a proper safety device that will eliminate (i) rise in pressure consequent on some possible defects in the evacuating system, and (ii) on the need for further evacuation after the desired condition is attained.

There are a few methods in common use for eliminating back suction but none of them would appear to be quite satisfactory. Among those which have been recommended, mention may be made of the use of (a) floating bobs (usually the section of a rubber stopper) enclosed in a cylindrical tube right above the passage that connects with the chamber under evacuation, and (b) simple valve arrangement by cutting a slit in the stopper (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1923, 15, 32). Both the above mentioned traps were tried by the author but found to be unsatisfactory.

The following is the description of the new check valve which can be made from materials found ordinarily in any laboratory. A fairly stout cylindrical glass tube (A) diameter of 3-4 cm. is drawn at one end (Fig. 1) into an L-shaped tube, the narrower end of

FIG. 1.

INNER SURFACE OF THE STOPPER

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

which will be connected to the suction pump. The other end is closed with a one-holed rubber-stopper; a tube (C) (diameter about 6 mm.) is passed through the stopper and pushed in just upto the surface without protruding into the space above. Covering the major portion of the surface of the same stopper is a thin strip of rubber (D) which is fixed in position with an adhesive. The position of the strip is indicated by the shaded portion in Fig. 2. Tube (B) which may be either fused in or fixed in position by a small rubber tube will be particularly useful, when a water pump is used. It helps to remove quickly any water that may collect on the top of strip D.

The valve thus prepared is mounted on a bottle which helps to keep it in a vertical position (Fig. 3). Where the valve is intended to maintain a very high vacuum (as when a Hyvac pump is used) a heavy metallic disc of diameter just wider than that of (A) and weighing about 100 g. will be useful in making the diaphragm settle evenly over the hole and thus effectively sealing the vacuum.

In actual use, this valve comes next to the pump so that when the pump is disconnected, the reduced pressure in the evacuated portion is maintained. Repeated trials have shown that once the required vacuum is attained, the pump can be disconnected without any rise in pressure and the reduced pressure maintained for several days.

The author's thanks are due to Professor V. Subrahmanyam, for his interest and helpful suggestions in the above investigation.